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NEW DEVICES
FOR
HYPOMAGNETIC FIELDS AND PREMISES RESEARCHING

The work is reported at the Crimean International Seminar
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in Partenit

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РОССИЙСКАЯ АКАДЕМИЯ НАУК

**ИНСТИТУТ ЗЕМНОГО МАГНЕТИЗМА, ИОНОСФЕРЫ
И РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЯ РАДИОВОЛН**

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**НОВЫЕ ПРИБОРЫ
ДЛЯ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ГИПОМАГНИТНЫХ ПОЛЕЙ И ПОМЕЩЕНИЙ**

Работа доложена на Крымском Международном семинаре
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The basic characteristics created in the initiative order and on means of the author of new samples of scientific devices are given. These devices are intended for detection of electromagnetic fields harmful artificial magnetic fields and radiations in conditions of urban dwelling-environment of the man and for realization of researches in hypomagnetic premises.

The basic materials of work were reported at the International Crimean scientific seminar "Space Ecology and Noosphere (CEN'99)", carried out from October 4 till October 9, 1999 in Partenit and at a seminar "Experience of creation, functioning and prospect of development of the regional informational-analytical centres of the ecological control and monitoring in Russian Federation", carried out from October 11 till October 15, 1999 in Zvezdnyi gorodok (Moscow Region).

Приведены основные технические характеристики созданных в инициативном порядке и на средства автора новых образцов научных приборов. Эти приборы предназначены для обнаружения электромагнитных полей, вредных искусственных магнитных полей и излучений в условиях городской среды обитания человека и для проведения исследований в гипомагнитных помещениях.

Основные материалы работы были доложены на Международном Крымском научном семинаре «Космическая экология и Ноосфера (CEN'99)», проводившемся с 4 по 9 октября 1999 г. в г. Партенит и на семинаре «Опыт создания, функционирования и перспективы развития региональных информационно-аналитических центров экологического контроля и мониторинга в Российской Федерации», проводившемся с 11 по 15 октября 1999 г. в Звездном городке.

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INTRODUCTION.

In 1971 in Moscow the symposium *"The Approaches to a Hygienic Estimation Constant and Infra-Low (50 Hz) Magnetic Fields"* was held, where for the first time was marked, that adverse influence can render not only strong artificial fields, but also artificial easing of a geomagnetic field (GMF). How to estimate influence of magnetic fields? It was offered in quality of a *"bench-mark level"* to use intensity natural GMF and then already to estimate this influence not in oerstedes, and in relative units describing "a degree of change of a magnetic field", keep in mind, that this unit can change on size and can be with alternating signs.

On various biological objects in the carried out experiments the researchers simulated of hypermagnetic conditions, used of hypermagnetic fields, that is magnetic fields considerably superior a level of natural GMF. These isolated and not systematized experiments differed on a way of creation of a magnetic field, its amplitude (from units oersted up to 200000 oersted) and on duration of influence (from minutes about months).

For a hygienic estimation of magnetic fields, first of all, it is necessary to divide *magneto sensitivity* (initial short-term reactions arising at the minimal duration of influence) and *magnetoaffection* (long, sometimes irreversible reactions to magnetic fields having property of accumulation - the cumulation). It is possible to consider proved, that organism is capable to react even to changes of a geomagnetic field amplitude, that is on oersted shares, and such reactions can serve an example of magneto sensitivity. The modern medicine-biological researches confirm an opportunity of active influence on the man electromagnetic field (EMF) of small power density. The special place is occupied in researches by effects of complex influence of constant and low-frequency magnetic fields. By one of mechanisms of EMF influence is connected to the phenomenon of a parametrical resonance of ions, which can result in changes in heart-vascular, immune, central nervous system to influence maximum nervous functions (memory, attention, speed of reaction, perception etc.).

Today is proved, that the magnetic field is necessary for considering as the unsuccessful factor of industrial environment, and at the further increase of its intensity in an industry the introduction of its control and professional - pathological estimations is necessary and necessarily. Therefore in April, 1999 at us in the country the Law of Russian Federation No 52-Φ3 "About Sanitary - Epidemiological Well-Being of the Population" was accepted.

What limiting admitted of magnetic fields intensity are possible on manufacture? What oerstedes are harmless? *A.M. Vyalov*, for example, considers, that the intensity of a magnetic field under production conditions at a level of hands should not exceed

300 oersted at a gradient 5... 20 oersted/centimeter. Some researchers consider, that threshold intensity of a magnetic field, at which there is an organism defeat, approximately on two order exceeds of GMF intensity. For example, J. Wikswo, on the basis of own accounts, asserts, that biological action can have only artificial magnetic field more than 200 mT.

The man, entering, for example, in the house of a ferro-concrete design, is exposed to change of a magnetic field in some thousand nT and does not feel such influence on organism as at influence, for example, magnetic storm (MS). The researches in this area show, that the mechanism of influence on the man is not clear. The methods of treatment by influence of strong constant fields are known, and also influence on alive organism weak on intensity (share of oersted) low-frequency variable fields, which frequency continuously varied from 0,01 up to 200 Hz. Many researchers give the important meaning of heterogeneity of a magnetic field and parity of size of heterogeneity of a field and his intensity [V.A. Druz', A.M. Serdyuk etc.]. The opinions express, that on result of biological experiment can render influence a direction of magnetic power lines.

For ordering available experimental data, their comparisons and comparisons, are very important are to known by dependence of biological effects on EMF parameters. In a complete kind these dependences remain while unexplored, but the information, saved to the present time, allows to make a conclusion, that the EMF biotropical effect at small and moderate intensity depends on frequency.

HYPOMAGNETIC FIELDS And DEVICES FOR THEIR MEASUREMENT

Hypomagnetic field (*weakened GMF*) is a magnetic field inside the usual or shielded premise, which is defined by a superposition of the magnetic fields created weakened GMF, field from ferromagnetic parts of a premise construction, field of a constant current proceeding on trunks, separate parts of a construction or inside it. The basic parameters of a hypomagnetic field are intensity of a vector of a constant magnetic field indoors, corner of an inclination of this vector indoors and gradient of intensity of a magnetic field between two points in space indoors. In opinion of Yu.G. Ryabov (NTC IRES), most informative is the relative criterion of hypomagnetic fields equal to size of easing of intensity of a magnetic field indoors concerning intensity of GMF natural open space outside of a premise, - K_h . As an example it is possible to result some characteristic meanings of GMF easing factor - K_h in various premises (in times): in wooden houses (1,05... 1,1), in inhabited ferro-concrete houses (1,15... 1,4), in motor vehicles (1,2... 4,0), in the underground (1,8... 11) and so on. The maximal meaning of GMF easing, known of information sources, makes about 100 times.

All is higher stated speaks that the meanings a component of a GMF vector inside and outside of any premise, as a rule, differ. It also does not allow to consider with high accuracy their those meanings, which are defined in nearby magnetic observatories.

Really, there are some features of magnetometer installation and application at use them in conditions of a local premise. The technique of use in these conditions is insignificant, but differs from work and installation of devices in magnetic observatory, as in observatory there are no rather large spatial gradients of a magnetic field, what have almost all houses and inhabited premises.

The researches have shown, that the long influence of hypomagnetic fields on the man results in decrease of his serviceability, negative action on his health [Z.N. Nachilnitskaya et al. and L.V.Pochodzey]. Such fields are biologically active factor causing a number of changes at physiological, biochemical and morphological levels of organism functioning. Is established, that the biological border dividing safe and harmful working conditions at presence of hypomagnetic fields in a premise is characterized in factor of easing of $K_h = 2$. At $K_h = 2 \dots 5$ the increase at 40 % of quantity of diseases at the people working in conditions of such premise is observed. At a finding of the man in artificial hypomagnetic conditions the changes of mentality are marked, there are non-standard ideas new images. At creation of hypomagnetic conditions (shielding of natural magnetic fields in 1000 times) the change rhythmic of cell division of a monolayer, degradation and destruction of mammals cells, infringement of development chicken embryo, occurrence of rough morphological changes of internal bodies of chickens is revealed.

Now in the IZMIRAN the initiative works on creation are conducted on the basis of modern microprocessor engineering intellectual magnetometers (IM) for an estimation of hyper- and hypomagnetic fields. For magnetic researches in premises of any type and size are created modern IM on the basis of small-sized fluxgate sensors, which allow to carry out certification of premises, them maping, definition of harmful sources of radiations. With the help of IM the opportunity has appeared to develop criteria of an hypomagnetic fields estimation in premises. The basic characteristics of IM, created in last years are resulted below.

THE INDICATOR of MAGNETIC CONDITIONS MAGIC MF-06 represents small-sized hand-held device with the built - in sensor and digital indicator allowing to define sources of harmful electromagnetic radiations of an artificial origin, rendering influence on the man on his workplace, on transport, and also to carry out the control of a level of magnetic conditions in electronic industry, in local and hypomagnetic premises.

The basic characteristics. Ranges of measurement of constant magnetic fields: 1, 2, . 20 and . 200 μT . Accuracy of the digital indicator accordingly 1, 10 and 100 nT. An error of measurement in each of measuring ranges no more than 1%. Power source 9 V from the battery of a "6F22" type. Consumed capacity in an autonomous mode no more than 0,12 W. A feeding of the device from a network of an alternating current by voltage 220 V, frequency 50 Hz is stipulated through the standard network adapter and output of an

analog signal on the analog recorder. A voltage of a constant current on an analog output 0... , 2,5 V. Dimensions: 160 x 65 x 25 mm. Weight of the device, no more than 0,15 kgs.

THE INDICATOR of MAGNETIC CONDITIONS IDL-08 represents small-sized hand-held device with the built - in graphic indicator allowing visualized the results of magnetic condition researching in a local premise as construction of magnetic maps and three-dimensional projections of a measured field instantly, in process or upon finishing of researches realization. The device uses the original filtration programs allowing to carry out of work in conditions with the large level of urban noises.

The basic characteristics. A range of measurement of constant magnetic fields is 200 μT . Accuracy of the graphic indicator at construction of magnetic cards is 0,1 μT . Consumed capacity in an autonomous mode no more than 0,45 W. A feeding from a network of an alternating current by a voltage 220 V, frequency 50 Hz is stipulated through the standard network adapter and output of digital data on PC through a serial port. Weight of the device, no more than 0,5 kgs.

ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELDS In INDUSTRIAL And INHABITED PREMISES And DEVICES FOR THEIR DETECTION

The monitoring of an environment through special devices allows to have complete representation about natural and presence of artificial electromagnetic radiations (EMR), "polluting" an environment. The modern small-sized portable devices on a basis of magnetolectrical sensors allow to carry out electromagnetic researches in premises of any type and size.

For electromagnetic researches the devices are created which allow to spend certification of premises, definition of harmful sources of radiations. Through such devices the opportunity has appeared to develop criteria of an EMR estimation in premises. The basic characteristics of the created devices are resulted below.

THE INDICATOR of ELECTROMAGNETIC CONDITIONS MAGIC MAF-08 is intended for definition of frequency and amplitude of sources of harmful electromagnetic radiations of an artificial origin rendering influence on the man, in frequency a range from 5 Hz up to 100 kHz.

The basic characteristics. A variable EMF measurement range: 0 ... 200 μT . A measurement error in a measuring range no more than 5%. Power source 9 V from the battery of a "6F22" type. Consumed capacity in an autonomous mode no more than 0,15 W. Dimensions: 140 x 82 x 36 mm. Weight of the device is no more than 0,25 kgs.

THE INDICATOR of ELECTROMAGNETIC CONDITIONS IDL-10 represents small-sized hand-held device with the built - in graphic indicator allowing visualized the results of research of electromagnetic conditions in a local premise as construction of a measuring EMF

spectrum in real time. Allows to carry out certification of industrial premises and workplaces with computer engineering.

The basic characteristics. A variable EMF measuring range: 0 ... 200 μT . Accuracy of the graphic indicator is 1%. Consumed capacity in an autonomous mode is no more than 0,35 W. A feeding from the storage battery and from a network of an alternating current by a voltage 220 V, frequency 50 Hz is stipulated through the standard network adapter and output of digital data on PC through a serial port. Weight of the device is no more than 0,5 kgs.

THE INDICATOR of ELECTROMAGNETIC CONDITIONS IDL-05. The device intended for continuous accumulation and storage of the data about environmental magnetic conditions in conditions of a local premise is developed [A.S.Zverev et al.]. It allows simultaneously to register the data from several magnetic sensors taking place in a premise. Capacity of non-volatile memory allows to keep the saved data within several day.

On the basis of the created devices the opportunity has appeared to carry out research works in clinics in conditions of city and in usual inhabited premises, at the rather large level of industrial and urban noises, where the magnetic field is strongly abnormal.

In the IZMIRAN, during a number of last years, the special works on research of electromagnetic conditions as in industrial, hypomagnetic and medical, and in inhabited premises [V.V.Lyubimov et al., Yu.I.Gurfinkel et al.] were carried out. The electromagnetic monitoring of industrial and inhabited premises, through the created devices, has allowed to carry out their certification, mapping, definition of harmful sources of radiations. By way of illustration we shall result some examples of inhabited and industrial premises mapping and examples of revealing of dangerous sources of electromagnetic radiations, which are shown on *Fig. 1 ... Fig. 5*.

Fig. 1. An example of a magnetic field abnormal source definition on proving ground.

Карта изодинам магнитного поля [Z-составляющая ВМИ] на уровне установки датчика диагностического магнитометра.

Fig.2. Examples of a magnetic field registration in usual apartments of usual dwelling houses.

Запись D в жилой квартире (3-й этаж 9-ти эт. ж\б дома).

Fig.3. Examples of registration of a source of electromagnetic radiation located behind a wall in the next apartment.

Fig.4. Examples of electromagnetic noise and handicaps record in day time and night time of day in the period and on a background of course magnetic storm on the 5-th floor of a Moscow Railway Hospital building.

Fig.5. Research of a magnetic field in hypomagnetic premise - shielded room from $Kh = 4 \dots 5$).

In equipment in such devices are interested both service of Sanitary-Epidemiological Supervision, and services engaged in construction and sale of dwellings, service of transport (is

especial of underground, where the people are subject strong pulse EMR), and also Centres of Electromagnetic Safety, created now in large industrial cities.

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NEW DEVICES FOR HYPOMAGNETIC FIELDS AND PREMISES
RESEARCHING

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НОВЫЕ ПРИБОРЫ ДЛЯ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ГИПОМАГНИТНЫХ ПОЛЕЙ И
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